

Political Liquidity and Administrative Resolve in Government Ministries: Four Cases from Ghana

Joseph Luna¹

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Abstract

What affects how ministers and senior bureaucrats in the Global South lead their ministries? This paper presents insights from the author's participant observation of four Government of Ghana Ministers and their senior bureaucratic staffs at Local Government and Rural Development; Tourism; Youth and Sports; and Roads and Highways. Engaging with the actual demands faced by politicians and bureaucrats, this paper develops a typology for understanding ministerial challenges based on the ministry's attractiveness as a source of political funds (political liquidity) and the extent to which a ministry can meet its core goals without depending on other entities (administrative resolve). This typology seeks to advance the discussion on how pockets of effectiveness are created and institutionalized and also to inform the practices of decision-makers to improve the provision of public goods and services.

Introduction

What affects how ministers and senior bureaucrats in Ghana lead their ministries? In challenging political environments, ministers and bureaucrats must possess both the political acumen and technical skill to achieve institutional change—that is, they must be ‘technopols’ (Dominguez 1996, Joignant 2011). In interviews, many ministers and bureaucrats point to intrinsic motivation and personal experience in explaining their actions and why they entered public service. Personality and charisma are indeed important. But beyond personal motivation, there are other factors—not to mention luck—that either impel or constrain these actors in their drive to effect change. Identifying those factors is critical to charting a way forward for diffusing the good practices from one pocket of effectiveness to the broader institutional landscape.

To understand ministers and bureaucrats, their intrinsic motivations, and the extrinsic forces that act upon them, this paper draws on an ethnographic study of four Cabinet of Ghana ministers and their senior staffs. In the early 2010s, the author shadowed the then-Ministers of Local Government and Rural Development; Tourism; Youth and Sports; and Roads and Highways, as they conducted their daily activities, both in the capital (Accra) and the rural districts. This “soak and poke” method can yield rich insights into how political and bureaucratic actors actually work (Fenno 1990). Ethnographic fieldwork helps establish stronger trust between a researcher and the persons they are studying. This trust can encourage the persons being studied to “open up” and share insights and regrets that might not otherwise become apparent.

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This work purposely focuses on ministries outside of those typically studied, such as ministries of finance. While ministries of finance are important subjects of study, they are not necessarily representative of the constraints and opportunities faced in other ministries, which typically have less exposure to aid donors. This paper joins other studies, such as Barma et al (2014) that focus on pockets of effectiveness that have been established in a more diverse array of government organizations.

Many would agree that political motivations influence the actions of ministers and bureaucrats. This paper offers an additional political consideration that has been little addressed in the pockets of effectiveness literature: political financing. How political activities are financed shapes the motivations and expectation of both political and bureaucratic actors (Luna 2020). Ministries provide, to the party in government, an attractive source of campaign funds, and both ministers and bureaucrats can find their work shaped by the party's financial need. With respect to political-bureaucratic relations in sub-Saharan Africa, this work furthers a growing recent literature on this topic (Brierley 2020, Rogger 2018). Ultimately, though, this work aims to serve as a reference for ministers, bureaucrats, and parties in government operating in challenging political environments. The ethnographic research detailed below will help build understanding of why some ministries may be more successful at delivering their mandates and also inform how ministers, bureaucrats, and parties can improve ministries' effectiveness.

Literature Review

Traditionally, the study of state capacity has focused on the state itself. However, there can be significant variation within a state's various public institutions. Roll (2013) posits that three problems need to be solved to cultivate the emergence of a bureaucratic pocket of effectiveness in a neopatrimonial setting. There is a problem of innovation, namely, how effective practices can even be introduced in difficult settings. Once such practices are introduced, there is the problem of control—that is, preventing those within the pocket of effectiveness from defecting from good practices. Lastly, there is the problem of organizational forging, or the institutionalization of good practices when there are many external incentives to defect.

In the Global South, pockets of effectiveness are frequently studied in the context of finance ministries (Hickey 2019). There are many reasons for why such pockets emerge in finance ministries. Compared to other (“line”) ministries, finance ministries typically offer higher pay as well as exposure to bilateral and multilateral development agencies. For civil servants in these finance ministries, exposure to external agencies both enhances technical skills and offers potential opportunities to gain valuable trainings or postings overseas. Additionally, the closeness of external agencies to these ministries—and the potential budgetary support that these agencies could offer—can impel ministries to perform better. Regardless of donor exposure, finance ministries are critical to state capacity. In Rwanda, Chemouni (2019) finds that the Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning is a critical instrument of elite legitimation—as such, the ministry's strong performance is of central interest to Rwanda's leadership. The support of the presidency was also critical to the strong performance of Zambia's Ministry of Finance; however, without that support, the Ministry's performance, along with that of the Zambian economy, has declined (Hinfelaar and Sichone 2019).

Though Ghana's Ministry of Finance has been identified as a pocket of effectiveness their effectiveness has varied over the post-independence period (Abdulai and Mohan 2019). McDonnell (2017), also focusing on Ghana's Ministry of Finance, develops the idea of the "interstitial bureaucracy", which refers to the social niches within a larger institution, whose practices are inconsistent with those of the larger whole. Examining the Ministry of Finance's highly effective Policy Analysis and Research Division (PARD), McDonnell (2017) describes its corporatist ethos, where bureaucrats arrive as early 6AM and do not depart until after 10PM. For the younger staff of PARD the long hours and relatively low pay present an opportunity to gain experience and exposure, ultimately opening up more lucrative careers beyond the civil service (McDonnell 2017).

While many scholars have focused on pockets of effectiveness connected to finance ministries, Barma, Huybens, and Viñuela, eds. (2014) investigate various effective institutions in The Gambia, Sierra Leone, East Timor, and Lao PDR. Similar to Roll's (2013) assertion of the 'control problem', Barma et al (2014) find that agency managers' ability to carefully manage relationships with elites is paramount. Nonetheless, there are different patterns by which agencies connect their actions with the broader institutional environment. Some institutions flourish because of elite commitment to that institution's mission (Barma et al 2014, Chemouni 2019). Other institutions capitalize on a window of opportunity to lock in reforms and institutionalize their autonomy. Lastly, other agencies build coalitions of support from clients and key stakeholders, mobilizing that support when needed (Barma et al 2014).

In the US context, pockets of effectiveness have been studied in several organizations. Kaufman (1960) analyzes bureaucratic culture in the US Forest Service, finding that a strong corporate ethos and clear mission, as established by the service's early leadership, help maintain the service's high performance. Carpenter (2001) assesses how mid-level bureaucrats in the US Postal Service forged bureaucratic autonomy by building coalitions with politically connected stakeholders. Wilson (1989), surveying an array of US bureaucratic institutions, recommends that executives understand the culture of their organizations—that is, the beliefs of their subordinates on the core tasks of the agency and the strengths and limitations of that culture. For Wilson (1989), agency managers can view their agencies from two perspectives: whether the activities of agency operators can be observed (outputs) and whether the results of those activities can be observed (outcomes).

The Case of Ghana

Ghana is a representative African case for a variety of reasons. Since the adoption of a democratic constitution in 1992, Ghana has witnessed relatively peaceful turnovers in power between its two major parties, the center-left National Democratic Congress (NDC) and the center-right New Patriotic Party (NPP). Currently, 275 Members of Parliament (MPs) are elected from single-member constituencies in plurality elections. The President is elected in a national, single-constituency election. While it is possible for different parties to hold the Presidency and a majority in Parliament, such a situation has yet to occur.

In the executive branch, the Cabinet of Ghana is led and selected by the President, though these selections may be subject to influence from the party leadership (Luna 2020). Cabinet ministers

head the various executive agencies in Ghana, such as the Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. Crucially, a majority of the Cabinet must be selected from sitting MPs. As a result, MPs in the governing party have a strong incentive to become Cabinet ministers. Cabinet positions are not only prestigious, but can also open lucrative avenues to contracts and political finance. Frequently, MPs lobby individual ministers for projects and funds to support constituencies, thus placing these ministers in powerful positions. Additionally, ministers, who are based in Accra, can more easily liaise with donors and investors to support their agendas.

Access to contracts can be critical to financing election campaigns in Ghana (Luna 2020). For ministers, these pressures can be amplified, especially if a political party expects ministers to support candidates besides themselves. Such pressure related to political financing is likely to affect how a minister does their job. In the most egregious case, a minister could direct contracts to a crony, ensuring that they receive a kickback of the funds. However, such an action is highly risky, and Ghana possesses a variety of institutions to combat grand corruption, such as the Commission on Human Rights and Administrative Justice and the Office of the Special Prosecutor. To avoid such attention, a minister (or other politician with procurement authority) could subtly influence procurement to steer contracts to contractors friendly to their political party. However, this kind of action would require the cooperation, whether active or passive, of the bureaucracy. Regardless, the political influence on procurement can negatively affect the quality of public goods that are delivered.

Bureaucrats in Ghana's ministries are relatively little studied, but their incentives and interactions with ministers can influence the quality of public-goods delivery. At the local-government level, Luna (2020) finds that bureaucrats are motivated by job security, but that they must also find ways to save for retirement, which can facilitate corruption related to procurement. Bureaucrats facing that pressure may overlook politicians taking kickbacks in exchange for taking kickbacks of their own. Brierley (2020) finds that Ghanaian bureaucrats who oppose politicians' corrupt activities may be transferred out of their positions. At the ministerial level, bureaucrats may be strongly motivated by a strong research ethos (McDonnell 2017), but they may also face personal pressures similar to those at the local-government levels (Price 1975).

Data

This paper examines four Ghanaian ministries—specifically, their ministers and senior bureaucrats—up close. At the time of study, the NDC was the governing party of Ghana. The study ministries were known at the time as: Ministry of Local Government and Rural Development; Ministry of Tourism; Ministry of Roads and Highways; and Ministry of Youth and Sports. To preserve their identities, the ministers will be referred to as follows: Minister A (Local Government), Minister B (Tourism), Minister C (Roads and Highways), and Minister D (Youth and Sports). Ministries will be referenced in a similar manner.

Table 1 highlights some key characteristics of the four ministries. The Ministry of Youth and Sports employs the fewest staff (54, at all grades), while the Ministry of Local Government and Rural Development (114) and Ministry of Roads and Highways (87) employ the most. The

Ministry of Youth and Sports also tends to employ a lower proportion of women and staff with at least bachelor’s degrees. The Ministry of Tourism employs the highest proportion of staff with at least bachelor’s degrees (37.7%).

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Sample Ministries

	Local Government	Tourism	Roads and Highways	Youth and Sports
Total staff	114	59	87	54
% women	40.4%	39.0%	43.7%	33.3%
Average age	46	46	45	43
% tertiary education	31.6%	37.7%	32.7%	24.5%
First appointments in civil service	17.3 years ago	14.8 years ago	17.2 years ago	14.2 years ago
Average tenure current ministry	Not available	4.5 years	Not available	6.3 years

Source: Office of the Head of the Civil Service.

The mission of the Ministry of Local Government and Rural Development (MLGRD) is to “promote good governance of the urban and rural communities through the formulation of policies and plans, coordination, monitoring, and evaluation of programs using highly trained and motivated staff and adoption of appropriate technology for national development.” (MOFEP 2019a) Some of the core functions of this ministry include designing and evaluating programs to reform local governments; effectively decentralizing public administration; promoting participation of civil society through community actions; and advising government on matters related to local development. While this ministry is charged with formulating the Government of Ghana’s local-development policies, the actual implementation of those policies is carried out by politically appointed District Chief Executives (DCEs), locally elected District Assemblies, and the Local Government Service bureaucracy. Given the widespread nature of this ministry’s work, policy and implementation across these entities can be disjointed.

The Ministry of Local Government and Rural Development was observed during a particularly exciting time in Ghanaian politics. Forty-six new districts were recently created, adding to the then-170 districts in the country, resulting in 216 total districts. The author joined the then-Minister for Local Government (Minister A) for a tour of several new districts as these districts prepared to be inaugurated. The new districts observed were diverse, located in the Ashanti, Brong Ahafo, Western, and Volta Regions of the country—including many areas that are not part of the NDC’s typical electoral strongholds.

The regional diversity of these new districts illuminates key realities of MLGRD. While this ministry’s mission revolves around decentralization and building capacity of local governments, that mission refers solely to the ministry’s technical mandate. In practice, this ministry—along with all ministries in this sample—has both a technical and a political mandate, the latter

corresponding to the interests of the party in power. Every Minister must keep these competing mandates in mind,

"In choosing a Minister, there are two criteria: loyalty and competence. And I would say loyalty counts for at least 80 per cent. Some competence is nice if you can get it." *Senior Bureaucrat, Ministry A*

Luckily, Minister A possessed both qualities of loyalty to the NDC as well as competence, having previously served in positions related to local governance. In preparing districts for inauguration, Minister A needed to forcefully articulate the government's support, particularly in areas more sympathetic to the opposition party. Decentralization, though it devolves power from the center, can serve to unify a country by providing better goods and services to its population.

"This district is very unified. There were NDC people and NPP people there, but they did not quarrel. This is what we expect." *Minister A*

Ultimately, though, the very selection of new districts—and, importantly, district capitals—is a political decision. While nominally there are formulas for the creation of new districts, Minister A made clear that a party in government can influence the selection of districts and district capitals.

"I have never regretted the decision of making this new district with [redacted] as its capital. Everyone needs to remember this day: we are making history. Ten, twenty years from now, our schoolteachers will say that this was the day in which [redacted] district was created. We even have historians from the US documenting this very event." *Minister A*

"Some say that we have created too many districts for Volta. The President said, 'No, look at the population. They need a district!' You deserve it, and we are ready to work for the development of Ghana." *Minister A*

From the bureaucratic standpoint, MLGRD faces several challenges. As Ghana adds more districts (currently, 260), MLGRD's oversight capacity must expand.

"This Ministry, in so many ways, it has really gone down. We are adding more and more districts, but the Ministry cannot handle it. It was better before." *Senior Bureaucrat, Ministry A*

With so many districts to nominally oversee, principal-agent problems can proliferate. At the district level, District Chief Executives represent the central government, and they can operate for long stretches without direct supervision from MLGRD.

"Our DCEs, they have become so silly-headed. Look at this one here! [...] When I was DCE, we would send someone to Brong Ahafo to spy on their projects there! We wanted to know what they were up to, and what we should do. It was like a competition. That is what is supposed to be happening now." *Minister A*

"The initiative is just not there." *Senior Bureaucrat, Ministry A*

Nonetheless, for many bureaucrats, MLGRD is an exciting challenge. For Ghanaians, local government is the front line of government, and there are many opportunities to effect positive change.

"I love the challenge that it gives me. There are many parts of Western [Region] that are very deprived. You get to write speeches, and other things, which I like, too, but above all it is the challenge." *Senior Bureaucrat, Ministry A*

However, MLGRD faces both technical and political mandates. Ministers (including Regional and Deputy Ministers) can disagree with technical staff and ultimately force a political solution.

"You see, I have to advise the Minister on what is good for the region and what is bad. The biggest challenge is when the Minister repeatedly does not agree with you; this happens when he wants expenditures to be one way, particularly if he is a prospective MP. If he is campaigning and gone, you have to make many decisions on your own, which can be very difficult. If something goes wrong, he and the press will blame it on you. It is important that the Regional Minister and the Coordinating Director be able to work together." *Senior Bureaucrat, Ministry A*

While the Ministry of Local Government and Rural Development forms a visible component of the Government of Ghana, it has an ever-expanding mandate without the concurrent rise in resources or legitimacy. The creation of districts is also more political than technical, which dilutes the technical role played by the MLGRD. Despite these challenges, MLGRD continues to exist and be seen as the ministry overseeing decentralization.

"You know what I think? They should eliminate the MLGRDE. It makes no sense. Right now, they want to consolidate the district health, education and agricultural offices and have them report to the local-government service and Ministry rather than to the sectoral heads. That makes no sense! The Ministry's authority is blurry. They should just get rid of it." *Senior Bureaucrat, Ministry A*

The Ministry of Tourism—now known as the Ministry of Tourism, Arts, and Culture—aims to “provide a firm, stable policy environment for effective mainstreaming of Ghanaian culture into all aspects of national life and to ensure the strong emergence of a vibrant creative economy to improve and advance the tourism industry.” Some of this ministry’s core functions include forming policy and programming for the development and promotion of domestic, regional, and international tourism; conducting research into regional and global trends in tourism, arts, and culture; and developing the human resources within the private and public sectors to effectively promote tourism, arts, and culture (MOFEP 2019c). At the time of this study, the Ministry of Tourism was relatively overlooked, but was in the process of standing up the Ghana Tourism Authority, which would serve as its implementing authority. Since then, the ministry has taken a central role in Ghana’s 2019 Year of Return activities, which have become globally known.

This Minister of Tourism (Minister B) is both a Cabinet Minister and a Member of Parliament (MP). For many Ghanaian MPs, becoming a minister is a central political goal. In addition to the prestige of being minister, that position grants significant access to contracts, donors, NGOs, and the private sector: avenues that could lead to lucrative positions after leaving (or losing) political office. Of course, this position also places sizeable pressure on the minister,

"Oh, these people! They are always asking you for money. We [Ministers] do not have that discretion! If I have to give them something, it comes out of my own salary." *Minister B*

The Ministry of Tourism faces a unique challenge: tourism, as a public good, can be difficult to measure and improvements to tourism may not be attributed to the ministry. In other words, the Ministry of Tourism depends upon the competence of other ministries, the private sector, and a host of other factors to be successful—most of which are beyond the ministry's control. Most of these other entities also compete with the ministry for credit for tourism-related inputs.

"Each government has its own focus areas. From 2003 to 2006, Tourism was totally left out of the Ghana Poverty and Reduction Strategy. However, under the current government, and GPRS II, Tourism now plays a prominent role." *Senior Bureaucrat, Ministry B*

"How do we get to our tourism sites if the roads are bad? We must consult the Ministry of Roads and Highways. The districts are supposed to look after their local sites; this is under the Ministry for Local Government. And if "culture" is involved, this falls under the Ministry of Chieftaincy and Culture. But we must talk to all of those places. It is not easy." *Senior Bureaucrat, Ministry B*

Additionally, bureaucrats report that the Ministry of Finance delays funding to Tourism, which hinders their ability to execute projects,

"Sometimes we have problems with the Ministry of Finance. They delay our disbursements of funding, and then we cannot do our projects!" *Senior Bureaucrat, Ministry B*

As a result, Minister B needs to be diplomatic in her interactions, even when her own staff falls short in carrying out their duties and coordinating with other ministries. Ministries with these inherently nebulous mandates require different ministers than, say, serial campaigners such as Minister A.

"I was sent [to my first Ministry] because it seemed to fit naturally with my interests. I overhauled [that Ministry]. I hired outside consultants to review the entire organization and make it better. That was all my initiative. If you go there today, they will tell you: she left a legacy." *Minister B*

Minister B is an overhauler of organizations. As Minister of Tourism, she must interface with numerous organizations: her bureaucratic staff, government colleagues, NGOs, the private sector, the diplomatic community, and so forth. There is a constant struggle to ‘define’ Tourism and achieve its goals—while also competing with other ministries for resources and recognition. As one director described the Minister’s duties,

“Your job is multifaceted, and you must be able to manage so many stakeholders: other Ministries, Departments and Agencies; the private sector; NGOs; traditional authorities; and so forth. As such, you must be approachable, you must listen, but you also need to be firm, or all these groups will walk over you. Politically, you will also be dealing with diplomats and MPs, and you must be able to adapt yourself.” *Senior Bureaucrat, Ministry B*

The bureaucrats of the Ministry of Tourism viewed the ministry as having particularly noble goals,

“You see, we are about integrating culture. We need Ghanaians to see more of their own country, to have more leisure. It is only then that we can reduce stereotypes and have a better country.” *Director, Ministry B*

However, such a goal is difficult to measure; as mentioned previously, the Ministry of Tourism is reliant on other ministries to provide public goods. If more Ghanaians are traveling, this could be because the economy has grown or transport is better—the Ministry of Tourism would need to more clearly claim credit for such gains in tourism.

This uncertainty of labor and credit affects the quality of bureaucrats’ work. The author observed the Ministry of Tourism preparing and executing one of its signature events, Panafest. Panafest, a cultural celebration hosted by Ghana every two years, brings together Ghanaians and members of the diaspora and diplomatic community for a variety of performances and artistic events. Some events include visits to the Cape Coast Castle and durbars with traditional leaders. Panafest is a major diplomatic and financial opportunity for Ghana, and there is a sense of competition with other African countries.

"If we are not careful, this event will be taken over by Nigeria. There is big competition for Panafest. But it is our baby." *Minister B*

However, three weeks prior to such an important event taking place, senior bureaucrats did not demonstrate a high degree of readiness,

"Funding? We do not have any. We tried to get some from the US Embassy but we have not heard back." *Senior Bureaucrat, Ministry B*

"Here we cut our coat according to the material rather than your size." *Senior Bureaucrat, Ministry B*

For Minister B, these interactions are frustrating, especially given the importance of Panafest. Being a Minister is already difficult, but for her the uncertain mandate of her ministry and diplomatic nature of her position presents a particular bind.

"That is the problem with the public service. I was so mad at them! But I have to be diplomatic. I cannot just say what I think. Otherwise, they will make life even more difficult for me ... They are permanent staff, but I am only temporary. They can do what they want, and soon I will be gone. But, here and there, you do find a few good civil servants who are very helpful." *Minister B*

The Ministry of Roads and Highways strives to “provide an integrated, efficient, cost-effective, and sustainable road transport system responsive to the needs of society, supporting growth and poverty reduction and capable of establishing and maintaining Ghana as a transportation hub of West Africa.” (MOFEP 2019b) Some of this ministry’s core functions include policy formulation and evaluation with respect to road infrastructure; infrastructure maintenance; and financing of road maintenance. This ministry has various implementing agencies, such as the Ghana Highways Authority. Given the visibility and importance of roads to local development in Ghana, this particular ministry (and its minister) receives significant attention from MPs.

The Minister for Roads and Highways (Minister C) is one of the more accessible ministers of this study sample, not just to the author but also to bureaucrats and fellow politicians. Such accessibility is not necessarily a feature of this particular individual, but is an expectation imposed upon leaders of this ministry. Compared to the other three ministries in the study sample, the Ministry of Roads and Highways has the clearest mission (at least in the eyes of the government and public) and it can claim significant credit or blame for highly visible projects.

Because of this visibility, Minister C finds himself engaged with more political work compared to the other ministries in this study.

"Oh, no, this is not really typical Minister work. It's for the [redacted] constituency, which is having a by-election. I'm just going up there to make sure that the roads are finished before the by-election happens. This thing is just political." *Minister C*

Political pressure may negatively impact the quality of the ministry’s work. While the bureaucrats of the Ministry of Roads and Highways are technical experts who compile rigorous statistical data, ultimately this ministry’s work answers to political principals. In Ghana, roads are visible political symbols, and bring significant credit-claiming opportunities for politicians, as well as opportunities to generate kickbacks and electoral funds from contractors (Luna 2020). As a result, Minister C needs to have much energy and courage to both entertain the political requests coming in from colleagues and avoid accusations of favoritism and corruption,

“You see, being Minister here requires fortitude. Fortitude. The President just called me one day, and said he needed me. Being Minister here, you have to keep running just to stay standing. Every day, people come in, and they will try to sway you. Even my own colleagues! One of the good things about [the President]: sometimes

people would come up to him and say, ‘Oh, this person is taking that money!’ It happened to me a few times! But the President would sit us all down, and hear everyone’s side. That really brought me close to him.” *Minister C*

Clearly the President’s support is essential for someone in Minister C’s position. Minister C must make difficult decisions about which roads may need more “political support”, a decision which likely creates enemies. The President’s backing lends legitimacy to Minister C.

Similar to the bureaucrats of the Ministry of Tourism, the bureaucrats at the Ministry of Roads and Highways manage a variety of stakeholders and pressures. However, unlike their counterparts at Tourism, bureaucrats at Roads and Highways are better resourced and, crucially, their Ministry has a clearer and more easily measurable mandate. Roads and road usage can be measured; indeed, external donors demand that the Ministry of Roads and Highways be equipped to contribute to feasibility studies for externally funded projects. Donors have played a significant role in shaping the structure of the Ministry of Roads and Highways.

"Back then, everything statistical was compiled by the Ghana Statistical Service. But it was the World Bank that changed all that in the 1980s. It was decided that we should get smaller units in each Ministry to link up with GSS for planning purposes. ... It was during those times that the World Bank gave us the structure that we have today. The Ministries were reorganized to have four mainline directorates: policy planning with monitoring and evaluation; finance and administration; human resources; and research, statistics and information." *Senior Bureaucrat, Ministry C*

Donors help ensure that the Ministry of Roads and Highways is well resourced, often providing funding for new data and training opportunities for staff. Compared to other ministries, bureaucrats at Roads and Highways likely have more opportunities to take training courses (especially overseas courses) and donor funding helps bureaucrats to undertake important projects. Such support likely improves the *esprit de corps* felt by a given bureaucracy.

“In 2004, with help from the Royal Danish Embassy, I started a database that compiles all the transport indicators.” *Senior Bureaucrat, Ministry C*

However, donor support can outweigh a given government’s priorities,

“In 2001, the new NPP government tried to combine the Ministry of Transport with Communications, as it was before. However, the World Bank said ‘no’, and it didn’t happen.” *Senior Bureaucrat, Ministry C*

Relative to the other ministries in the study sample, the Ministry of Roads and Highways has a chief director most resembling a “technopol”. That is, the bureaucrat-in-charge had both technical acumen as well as the political skill to work with the Minister and other political figures to ensure effective technical advising. A competent chief director can help ensure that the ministry’s partnerships with donors are well executed.

“I have a Chief Director who really knows how to link up with the Minister. For data, we are all right. The Minister gets what he needs from our data. If there is a strong bond between the Minister and the Chief Director, and they can relate on a daily basis, then that is good [...] Of all the chief directors I have had, this one is exceptional. You know, it is a political appointment, but he is very on top and very fair. As a director, I do not often see the Minister. We go through my boss, the chief director. If he can solve it, then why go to the Minister?” *Director, Ministry C*

Informally, many bureaucrats admitted to the author that appointments for chief directors are politically controlled. Some chief directors lack technical skill and bring more political concerns to a given Ministry; other chief directors, however, are technically strong and relate well to the bureaucratic staff. The level of focus that politicians and donors concentrate upon the Ministry of Roads and Highways likely demands the appointment of a competent chief director. For the many government politicians and donors vying for successful projects, there must be assurance that the Ministry of Roads and Highways can deliver on its mandate.

The goal of the Ministry of Youth and Sports is to “contribute to the attainment of national integration, sustained macro-economic stability, peace, healthy population, and the Sustainable Development Goals through youth development and empowerment, and promotion of sports.” (MOFEP 2019d) Some of the ministry’s core functions include promoting the organization and development of mass participation in amateur and professional sports; empowering the youth through education and skill training to develop their potential in response to the labor market; and providing skills training and job opportunities for unemployed youth. Compared to the other ministries in this sample, the Ministry of Youth and Sports has a somewhat divergent set of core functions, as evidenced by its very name. Many of the core functions overlap with those of other ministries, such as the Ministry of Employment and Labour Relations. Additionally, the Ministry of Youth and Sports has powerful constituents, including the Ghana Football Association.

Though the Ministry of Youth and Sports may not appear to as high profile as other ministries, such as Roads and Highways, it is a significant target for corruption and political favors.

"You see, people here tend to be greedy. It is a problem all over: FIFA, the Olympics, etc. Sports generates money. You need caterers for these events, facilities, transport, etc. A lot of the people here are affiliated with private businesses, and they try to funnel the contracts to them. We handle a lot of money at this Ministry. While the people here might not get their hands directly on the money right away, they get some of the benefits further downstream." *Minister D*

The political allure of Roads and Highways is visible: politicians can claim credit for bringing roads to their constituencies, and can also benefit from beneficial awarding of contracts. With Youth and Sports, the payoff is less visible but more convertible: awarding a variety of contracts to party supporters can lead to a more direct transfer of funds. Additionally, compared to Roads and Highways, the Ministry of Youth and Sports appears to receive much less attention from donors, which likely lowers the risk of corrupt activities being detected and punished.

However, while Roads and Highways has a relatively clear, visible mission, the Ministry of Youth and Sports is divided between two different areas. In trying to accomplish goals for each area, the Ministry of Youth and Sports finds itself in a position similar to that of Ministry of Tourism: having to coordinate across different ministries, rather than being able to “take the lead” in a specific area.

"Oh yes, I have to work with both the Ministries of Education and Employment & Social Welfare. They can be difficult—especially the Ministry for Employment & Social Welfare. The people there, they think they can do everything. But they lack the capacity. As you were saying, it is turf, it is territory. They see you try to do something that ever slightly falls under their mandate, and they get upset. They thwart you. Even at the Ministry of Health, they can get in our way. There are youth-related health problems, too! Take HIV/AIDS, for instance. There are all these things that we can do together, but they will not have it." *Minister D*

Compounding these coordination problems, the Ministry of Finance can limit funding allocations to this Ministry,

"They place a ceiling on things. I don't know where it comes from, to be honest. But when they place that ceiling, we have to make note of the difference. And you see here, we get funding from outside to do our own programs. So there is the Government of Ghana budget at the Ministry of Finance, but here at this Ministry we have two budgets." *Minister D*

“Sometimes there are things that you want to do, then you realize that the Ministry of Finance is not releasing the funds.” *Senior Bureaucrat, Ministry D*

It would seem that, with these different turf wars and funding shortfalls, a Minister could try to reach out to fellow Ministers to negotiate compromises. However, Minister D is not optimistic that fellow ministers would listen,

"[laughing] It is not that easy. You can't just 'talk' to your fellow Ministers. You see, ideally, we would view our work in Ghana from a nationalistic sense. Of course the Ministries would work together: Youth problems require input from Education and Employment and Health. They are all important, and they naturally overlap. But, no, in this country it is about power. Accumulating power.” *Minister D*

For the bureaucrats of the Ministry of Youth and Sports, corrupt outside influences affect the quality of work and the ability to exercise bureaucratic discretion.

“I came across an idea from Marcel Desailly, the French football star. His mother is Ghanaian, and he lives here now and has built a large complex that can be used to house Ghanaian footballers for tournaments and training. He was prepared to give it to us for a lower rate, and he brought a proposal,

which I helped handle. But there was no decision. There is a status quo here, where the footballers all stay at expensive hotels at great expense to the state.” *Senior Bureaucrat, Ministry D*

As for why footballers stay at expensive hotels at great expense to the state,

“It is corruption. Many of the people here have links to those hotels ... It is that letters frequently go missing here in the system. This really limits your access to the Minister. You don’t know what happened. Is the letter actually lost? Did someone take it? You don’t know.” *Senior Bureaucrat, Ministry D*

Overall, bureaucrats at Youth and Sports report having very little discretion in their jobs,

“The discretion is very limited. I have to clear things with my boss, and he has to bring it to the Minister. The final decision rests with the Minister, even more than the Chief Director.” *Senior Bureaucrat, Ministry D*

The political pressures and mission uncertainty facing the Ministry of Youth and Sports would challenge any minister. Though Minister D projected an air of calm command during the author’s study, he preferred the work of a Member of Parliament,

"To be honest, I do not want to be a Minister. I would rather just be an MP, and doing my committee and constituency work. I feel that I really have an effect there [...]A lot of these politicians become Ministers, and they just use it to take money. They like the position, the prestige, everyone calling them 'Minister'. They all have their entourage, their drivers, their guards. Why do I need a guard?! Is there going to be a terrorist attack on youth policy?!" *Minister D*

Discussion

It is clear that Ministers, Ministries, and senior bureaucrats face challenges beyond providing public goods and services. Ministries can be attractive sources of political funds for parties in power, and Ministers face pressure from party supporters to make contracts and other opportunities available. The pressure from parties to extract political funds would challenge any bureaucratic entity seeking to innovate and institutionalize good practices, as framed by Roll (2013). Additionally, while some ministries can take the lead in well-defined areas of influence, other ministries must coordinate a variety of entities to achieve successes. Such coordination complicates bureaucratic leaders’ abilities to monitor the outputs and outcomes generated by an agency (Wilson 1989).

The findings from the four ministries above highlight two key features, which I term political liquidity and administrative resolve. Political liquidity, which is derived from the financial term, liquidity, refers to the ease with which the products of a government agency’s efforts can be turned into financial gain for the governing party. Administrative resolve refers to the ease with which a government agency can execute its mandate without depending on other entities. I will

describe these terms further below, but it is important to note that most agencies likely exhibit features of both of these definitions.

Political liquidity is important because, for any governing party in a democratic country seeking to win and stay in power, it is essential to be able to finance electoral activities (Luna 2020). Holding ministerial portfolios is one avenue towards accessing such finance. Compared to claiming credit for infrastructure projects or policies, the money generated through political liquidity is important because such money can be funneled to a variety of political-party priorities: political money is not necessarily constrained to a particular time and place, as a road or clinic might be. Political money generated by one activity can be transferred to another part of the country. Procurement corruption provides opportunities to generate political money. If a party's preferred contractor "wins" the contract for a road, school, school equipment, medical equipment, festival supplies, etc., a party can receive kickbacks from that contract. Such funds may be available relatively quickly (though there can be funding delays) for political use, such as buying votes or providing private goods to supporters. To some extent, since most government agencies engage in procurement processes, there are opportunities to generate political liquidity in any agency; however, some agencies may be more conducive to political liquidity than others.

On the other hand, political illiquidity does not necessarily mean that a party cannot derive political gains from a particular agency's output; rather, that output is less easily convertible into money. For example, government policies—such as fiscal policy or foreign policy—are not themselves politically liquid: there is little actual money that can be immediately derived from implementing such policies. However, a party in government can certainly claim credit for implementing those policies, potentially winning votes in that regard.

Administrative resolve refers to agencies that can accomplish their visible mandates relatively on their own. Such agencies typically have a clear mission that focuses on a specific, easy-to-define area, and these agencies are viewed by other agencies and the public as being "in charge" of a given area. Other agencies defer to this agency when conducting work in its area. In this study, I term these agencies, "resolving agencies". To accomplish tasks in their areas, these agencies can resolve to complete them, while not being dependent on the actions of other agencies.

I term the counterpoint to resolving agencies, "coordinating agencies". These agencies typically have mandates that are less clear and measurable, or they may be compelled to fulfill multiple mandates. Coordinating agencies may be lower priorities for a government, and fellow agencies may not view them as having the "final word" in a given area. In short, these agencies are compelled to work with other agencies to accomplish their mandates, and their success is dependent on the actions of other agencies. Of course, every government agency, to some extent, must coordinate with other agencies, but, in this formulation coordinating agencies are dependent on others.

Table 2 demonstrates how the four study ministries align with the classifications of political liquidity and administrative resolve.

Table 2. A Typology of Political Liquidity and Administrative Resolve

	Resolving Agency	Coordinating Agency
Politically Liquid	Roads and Highways	Youth and Sports
Politically Illiquid	Local Government	Tourism

The Ministry of Roads and Highways typifies a politically liquid resolving agency. Their mandate is relatively clear, and the quantity and quality of roads and highways can be easily measured. That is not to say that this ministry does not coordinate with others—such as Finance, Local Government, Transport, and Agriculture—but the Ministry of Roads and Highways is seen as in charge of roads and highways, as evidenced by the support received from donors. While there are clear avenues for politicians to claim credit for newly built or rehabilitated roads, this ministry can also generate political liquidity. Building and rehabilitating roads generates opportunities to procure contractors for a variety of services, and those contractors can be supporters of the party in government. Contract kickbacks help finance a party’s operations.

The Ministry of Youth and Sports can be classified as a politically liquid coordinating agency. Its mandate is divided between two distinct areas (youth policy and sports policy), and it depends on other ministries’ actions to accomplish its goals. For example, many of the ministry’s vendors receive lucrative tax breaks for their work with the ministry; such tax breaks are provided by the Ministry of Finance. In accomplishing its youth training and educational goals, this ministry works with the (then-called) Ministry of Employment and Social Welfare; it is not clear which of those ministries might get more credit for improving youth welfare, which can result in turf wars. With respect to political liquidity, the Ministry of Youth and Sports offers numerous contracting opportunities, especially with respect to sports. Sports vendors (e.g., venue hosts, accommodations, food providers, etc.) sympathetic to the party in government can receive contracts and pay kickbacks to the party, resulting in funding of the party coffers.

The Ministry of Local Government and Rural Development represents an agency that is politically illiquid but also a resolving agency. As evidenced above, this ministry’s work is certainly political in nature: the selection of new districts and district capitals can be a political process, and can win votes in a given area. However, those political gains are not necessarily liquid: a new district capital in one part of Ghana, does not necessarily win votes in another part of the country, nor does it directly generate money, as contracts might. While this ministry may not generate political liquidity, it can be classified as a resolving agency. When it comes to inaugurating new districts or overseeing the Local Government Service (the bureaucrats at the district level), this ministry is seen as being in charge, despite some internal bureaucrats’ views that the ministry should not exist. The ministry does coordinate with other entities (e.g., Food and Agriculture, Health, Education), but it is clearly the ministry charged with implementing local governance.

The Ministry of Tourism is politically illiquid and a coordinating agency. Like other ministries there are contracting opportunities for tourism operators; however, compared to Youth and Sports and Roads and Highways, party-affiliated contractors seem to bother this ministry less. Additionally, during the time of study, Tourism was not a major focus of government compared to other ministries, which may have dampened demand for political liquidity. With respect to

administrative resolve, this ministry is a coordinating ministry. Tourism depends on the actions of other agencies to accomplish tourism-related goals, and the Minister of Tourism needs to be diplomatic to ensure support from these agencies, the private sector, and the donor community.

It is important to note that no particular category described above is necessarily “better” or “worse” than another category: the categories merely shape how a minister and senior bureaucrat may interact with a particular ministry and its stakeholders. While a politically illiquid ministry may appear to be safer from political interference (e.g., a Ministry of Finance), it may also be the case that the ministry is not viewed as important by the government. Conversely, a politically liquid ministry does not necessarily have to attract unqualified contractors and such a ministry can give a minister an opportunity to improve systems, while still offering opportunities to party-supporting contractors,

"Well, I created a deposit system where contractors must place money down. If they don't do the job satisfactorily, then we fire them and take their deposit. I have also had to make sure that the rules are very clear, and that all know what they are doing." *Minister D*

Minister D’s initiative to create a deposit system can both help ensure that contractors perform quality work and establish the ministry’s commitment to monitor contractors’ work to completion. As studied by Williams (2017), a lack of political commitment can result in significant levels of project non-completion.

With political liquidity, the nature of political interference is important in shaping the outputs and outcomes generated by a ministry. Party chairs and power brokers can pressure ministers and other senior politicians to generate funds and opportunities for party supporters; if those ministers and senior politicians refuse, party chairs and brokers have numerous mechanisms to remove them from power (Luna 2020). When the extraction of money from ministerial contracts negatively affects the quality of work (i.e., by awarding contracts to less qualified partisan contractors), then a ministry is more likely to fail in providing public goods and services. However, political interference may improve the quality of public goods and services if voters demand higher quality of those goods and services.

Turning to administrative resolve, it is likely easier for a government agency to accomplish its goals if it is a resolving agency, and is seen by other government agencies as being in charge of its particular area. However, resolving agencies may be less likely to spread their good practices and more likely to retain high-quality staff—at the expense of other agencies. Thus, resolving agencies may actually hinder the spread of pockets of effectiveness. A coordinating agency, however, faces a difficult task in accomplishing its goals, since it is dependent on the actions of other agencies. However, if a coordinating agency manages to successfully corral other agencies and be a pocket of effectiveness in that regard, then it may help spread effective practices across other agencies. Since all agencies, including resolving agencies coordinate with others, the coordinating agency has a potentially valuable role in improving administrative practices.

For a minister or politically appointed bureaucrat starting a new portfolio, it is important to remember the distinctions of political liquidity and administrative resolve. A political appointee

likely understands that a given ministry may face pressures to finance a political party's activities. Any minister or senior bureaucrat would likely be unsuccessful in overturning such a dynamic; indeed, they would likely not be appointed to such a ministry in the first place. However, can such a minister or senior bureaucrat convince the party in power to ensure that the ministry provides quality public goods while still being a source of political liquidity? Ideally, political funds should not have to come from ministries or contracting or non-transparent sources, but such an ideal has yet to be realized.

A minister that inherits a coordinating agency will likely have a more difficult job than a minister inheriting a resolving agency. This minister will have to build and maintain relationships across agencies, the private sector, the donor community, and within their own bureaucracies—tasks that only become more difficult as entities come and go. Given the pressures of generating political funds and support as a minister, establishing a model pocket of effectiveness may be too difficult of a task. Coordinating ministries face a problem of legitimacy in carrying out their missions. Could a party in government appropriately empower a coordinating ministry to have the “final word” in its area and convince other entities to respect that legitimacy? Could a minister of a coordinating ministry then establish a pocket of *sufficient* effectiveness: an entity—or part of an entity—that performs reasonably well while meeting (modest) political needs?

For parties in government and their supporting brokers, it is important to recognize the importance of political liquidity and administrative resolve. While extracting political liquidity from some agencies in the short-term may have immediate benefits, there may be long-term disadvantages to not providing quality public goods (e.g., lower overall trust in government). Political parties should deliberate with their own power and financial brokers, as well as other political parties, on whether these short-term pressures outweigh long-term needs. Perhaps establishing pockets of sufficient effectiveness may be an incremental step towards improving provision of public goods and services while decreasing political pressure on bureaucratic tasks.

With respect to coordinating agencies, parties in government should closely consider the underlying reasons for ‘why’ an agency plays more of a coordinating than resolving role. Some agencies are given multiple, distinct mandates to fulfill: for example, Youth and Sports; Employment and Social Welfare; Water Resources, Works, and Housing. For some agencies, multiple mandates may be sensible, whereas for other agencies the combination is not sensible (e.g., Transport and Communications). Parties in government could seek to ensure that ministries at least have clear, rather than competing, mandates.

Conditional on ministries having clear mandates, Presidents and parties in government should make clear to all ministers which ministries are in charge of key priorities and those whose coordinating roles in given areas should be respected by other ministries. The Ministry of Tourism lacked the legitimacy to ensure that other ministries and entities met its demands to execute Panafest; however, had the President and party in government given strong legitimacy to Tourism, then it could have carried out its coordinating mandate more easily. There will likely be disputes between Ministries and Ministers about ‘turf’, but Presidents and parties in government can use Cabinet sessions and other meetings to moderate between ministries; regardless, the legitimacy conferred on a particular ministry should be clear.

For donors, it is essential to remember political liquidity and administrative resolve when working with governments. A particular ministry may be a target for extracting money, but donors can help ministers and senior bureaucrats ensure that qualified contractors are selected. Similarly, in working to strengthen bureaucratic pockets of effectiveness, donors should ensure that they are not just working with resolving agencies, but also with coordinating agencies who can help spread better practices. Donors can help governments lend legitimacy to important coordinating agencies.

Conclusion

Through participant observation and elite interviews, this paper examines the actions of ministers and senior bureaucrats from four Government of Ghana ministries: Local Government and Rural Development; Tourism; Roads and Highways; and Youth and Sports. Based on these observations, ministries can be classified according to two criteria: political liquidity and administrative resolve. Political liquidity refers to the ease with which an agency's outputs and outcomes can be converted into political finance for the party in power, which can then use those funds to buy votes, provide public goods, and build support across the country. Administrative resolve refers to whether a given agency can accomplish its mandate primarily on its own or whether it is dependent upon the actions of other agencies to accomplish its mandate.

Political liquidity and administrative resolve affect the generation, sustainability, and dissemination of pockets of effectiveness. Where political liquidity permeates and negatively impacts an agency's outputs, pockets of effectiveness are unlikely to be generated and sustained. Where coordinating agencies struggle to achieve their missions, it is likely that the quality of their outputs will also suffer. It is up to government leaders and parties in government to ensure that politically liquid agencies enforce quality standards and that coordinating entities are appropriately legitimized.

References

- Abdulai, Abdul-Gafaru and Giles Mohan. 2019. "The Politics of Bureaucratic 'Pockets of Effectiveness': Insights from Ghana's Ministry of Finance." Working Paper.
- Barma, Naazneen; Huybens, Elisabeth; and Viñuela, Lorena, eds. 2014. *Institutions Taking Root: Building State Capacity in Challenging Contexts*. Washington, DC: World Bank Group.
- Brierley, Sarah. 2020. "Unprincipled Principals: Co-Opted Bureaucrats and Corruption in Ghana." *American Journal of Political Science*, 64(2).
- Carpenter, Daniel. 2001. *The Forging of Bureaucratic Autonomy: Reputations, Networks, and Policy Innovation in Executive Agencies, 1862-1928*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Chemouni, Benjamin. 2019. "The Rise of the Economic Technocracy in Rwanda: A Case of a Bureaucratic Pocket of Effectiveness or State-Building Prioritisation?" Working Paper.

Dominguez, Jorge. 1996. *Technopols: Freeing Politics and Markets in Latin America in the 1990s*. University Park, PA: Penn State Press.

Fenno, Richard. 1978. *Home Style: House Members in Their Districts*. Boston, MA: Little, Brown.

Hickey, Samuel. 2019. "The Politics of State Capacity and Development in Africa: Reframing and Researching Pockets of Effectiveness." Working Paper.

Hinfelaar, Marja and Justine Sichone. 2019. "The Challenge of Sustaining a Professional Civil Service Amidst Shifting Political Coalitions: The Case of the Ministry of Finance in Zambia, 1991-2018." Working Paper.

Joignant, Alfredo. 2011. "The Politics of Technopols: Resources, Political Competence, and Collective Leadership in Chile, 1990-2010." *Journal of Latin American Studies*, 43(3).

Kaufman, Herbert. 1960. *The Forest Ranger: A Study in Administrative Behavior*. Washington, DC: Resources for the Future.

Luna, Joseph. 2020. *Political Financing in Developing Countries: A Case from Ghana*. Abingdon, UK: Routledge.

McDonnell, Erin. 2017. "Patchwork Leviathan: How Pockets of Bureaucratic Governance Flourish Within Institutionally Diverse Developing States." *American Sociological Review*, 82(3).

Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning. 2019. "Medium-Term Expenditure Framework (MTEF) for 2019-2022: Ministry of Local Government and Rural Development."

Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning. 2019. "Medium-Term Expenditure Framework (MTEF) for 2019-2022: Ministry of Road and Highways."

Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning. 2019. "Medium-Term Expenditure Framework (MTEF) for 2019-2022: Ministry of Tourism, Arts and Culture."

Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning. 2019. "Medium-Term Expenditure Framework (MTEF) for 2019-2022: Ministry of Youth and Sports."

Price, Robert. 1975. *Society and Bureaucracy in Contemporary Ghana*. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press.

Rogger, Daniel. 2018. "The Consequences of Political Interference in Bureaucratic Decision-Making: Evidence from Nigeria." Working Paper.

Roll, Michael. 2013. "Pockets of Effectiveness: Why Do Strong Public Institutions Exist in Weak States?" APSA 2013 Annual Meeting Paper.

Williams, Martin. 2017. "The Political Economy of Unfinished Development Projects: Corruption, Clientelism, or Collective Choice?" *American Political Science Review*, 111(4).

Wilson, James. 1989. *Bureaucracy: What Government Agencies Do and Why They Do It*. New York, NY: Basic Books.